

ENHANCING A TEACHER'S PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCY IN A HIGHER EDUCATION SETTING

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Abstract:

Understanding the forms and techniques of teaching various courses in higher education institutions must be revised constantly in light of modern realities. The application of interactive techniques in teaching. Students can develop their knowledge and skills in managing information sources, interacting with other participants in the educational process, and problem-solving techniques in an environment that is designed to stimulate their creative activity through the use of interactive educational formats, methods, and means.

Key words: Education, society, competence, teacher, technologies, educational and mentoring process.

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The current society creates a social need in an era that is able to live and create in a state of intellectually intensive, research-intensive and information-rich innovations; it requires the development of research and action skills in the ever-changing world of generations, business, society and political life. In such a society, the most important place is not computers or machines, but knowledge and inventive thinking. Therefore, it is important to create our own science and effectively coordinate its achievements within a generation. Then, in the near future, we will need thousands of deeply qualified masters and graduate scientists in hitherto unexploited logical and specialist fields - biotechnology, nanotechnology, space transportation and information and communication technology.

Strategies in the conditions of the modernization of teaching, the current university professor must be ready and able to recognize changes in generalizations in his demanding behavior and professional activity. And for that it is not enough to simply encourage the subject to "follow the times"; in addition, the ability to self-educate, competent and individual self-development is essential. Such competence is difficult to assume when comparing the knowledge and skills that allow a person to develop professionally, to change behavioral characteristics, skillful actions and tendencies, to be objective and confident in decision-making, and to manage mental and emotional states.

Thanks to this, the skill characteristics of teachers of higher education institutions begin to more regularly include a combination of individual and competent characteristics and related self-regulation skills, which are able to characterize the level of individual and competent development. In addition, the professional advancement cannot be separated from the individual, because

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both are based on the guideline of self-development, which determines the ability to transform the movement of a demanding life into a protest of viable change.

As a result of this, identity comes to the beat frame of way of life movement – inventive self-actualization. Coordination competence approach into the higher instruction framework, which centers on the instruction result in case when the result is considered not as entirety of the obtained data but as a person's capacity to act completely different circumstances, is pointed at moving forward the interaction with human assets showcase, increment of specialists' competitiveness and overhaul of the substance, technique and journalist instruction environment. The unused instruction worldview infers the got to give a understudy not as it were with a whole of information, but too with a set of key competencies, which permit adaptably adjusting in powerfully changing social and financial conditions and utilizing the information in making modern competitive items and administrations.

Display circumstance requires the explore for extraordinary instruction shapes, which are essential for planning fruitful and requested by the human assets showcase masters, who have certain individual qualities. In conclusion we would like to title a number of prioritized objectives for moving forward proficient competence of a college instructor: creating a program for instructive and systematic supply of a modern era; characterizing instruction substance and structure; and considering the nature of teachers' proficient competence advancement within the professionalization handle.

Deep learning analyzes the problem of developing key skills- educational, communication and problem-solving skills. Enlightenment expertise gives the student the skills to manage the data and fields contained in the subjects in one comprehensive world. Real data objects (television, tape recorder, telephone, fax machine, computer, printer, modem, copier) and data transmission (audio and video recording, e-mail, mass media, network) help create skills to independently view, analyze and select important data, organize, change, save and share.

Competence could be a combination of basic knowledge and individual characteristics that enable a professional approach and expert understanding of providing knowledge, logical and healthy movement issues. The competency-based approach to teaching has recently become a protest of active understanding in education and training. In addition, it is recognized that logical improvements to the competency approach await guidance. The basic categories of the non-use approach are the concepts of "competence" and "competence". The term "competence" is not like one of the categories of basic education, but also a matter of intrigue.

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